

FORMULATION AND *IN-VITRO* EVALUATION OF BILAYER TABLET CONTAINING NARATRIPTAN HCL AND NAPROXEN USING NATURAL POLYMERS

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ABSTRACT

The objective of show work was to define and assess bilayer tablet of Naratriptan and Naproxen for treating migraine successfully. The Combining Naratriptan and Naproxen gives extra benefits in comparison with either medicate alone and can be considered for patients whose quality of life is impeded by migraine. When tablets of the combination of these are arranged, they tend to ended up unsteady amid the rack life of the detailing. Subsequently it is prescribed to get ready a bilayer tablet, by defining Naproxen in supported release layer and Naratriptan as quick discharge layer because it moves forward and increments the soundness by decreasing the corrosive base intelligent of both the drugs in combination there by expanding the bioavailability. Taking this into consideration diverse details were arranged by damp granulation strategy utilizing characteristic Tamarind Seed Polysaccharide and engineered HPMCK100, K15M discharge rate controlling hydrophilic polymers. The details were assessed for hardness, weight variety, friability, swelling file and medicate substance consistency. The in vitro discharge of medicate from the details was considered in P^H 1.2 acidic buffers and P^H 7.4 phosphate buffers, and it was found that the arranged tablets were able to support the discharge of the medicate up to 12hours. The discharge of Naratriptan and Naproxen of both layers from the tablets was found to be dissemination controlled and the discharge Component was non-Fickian based on the n esteem of Korsmeyer-peppas plot. The FTIR considers were performed from the watched crests it is clear that the polymers utilized and the drugs were found to be commonly congruous chemically. The defined bilayer tablets utilizing common polymers given quick discharge of Naratriptan and sustained discharge of Naproxen and thus hold guarantee as an elective dose shape within the treatment of migraine successfully.

Keywords: Naratriptan, Naproxen, Tamarind Seed, HPMCK100, K15M

INTRODUCTION

Oral delivery is the most commonly used method of drug delivery. Oral delivery allows patients to self-administer medications at any time of the day. However, there are many challenges associated with oral delivery, including poor patient compliance due to unpleasant taste, side effects, and gastrointestinal discomfort. To overcome these issues, researchers have focused on developing novel oral delivery systems that provide sustained release of active ingredients. These systems allow for a gradual increase in drug concentration in the body over an extended period of time, resulting in improved therapeutic efficacy and reduced toxicity^{1,2}.

Recently, a new generation of drug combination products with immediate-release and extended-release components has been approved by the regulatory authorities³. Such dosage forms have several advantages, but there are still some problems, such as physical incompatibilities, chemical incompatibilities, etc., in the manufacture of such dosage forms. Therefore, bilayer and multi-layer tablets are referred to as novel drug delivery systems. Arthritis is inflammation of the joints. It can affect one joint or multiple joints. There are more than 100 different types of arthritis, with different causes and treatments. The two most common types are osteoarthritis (OA) and rheumatoid arthritis (RA). The best known treatment for arthritis is the use of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs).

Bilayer tablets are tablets that contain the same (homogeneous) or different (heterogeneous) subunits. Bilayer tablets are manufactured with a drug layer for immediate release and a second layer for releasing the drug itself Second dose or extended release. These tablets are suitable for sequential release of the combination of two active ingredients, separation of two incompatible substances, and different release profiles of the two active ingredients⁴.

Naratriptan is a triptan medicine used to treat migraine headaches. It is a selective 5-HT₁ receptor subtype agonist. The cause of migraine is not clearly explained; however, the effectiveness of naratriptan and other triptans is believed to be due to their activity as 5-HT (serotonin) agonists⁵.

Naproxen is a nonselective COX inhibitor. As an NSAID, naproxen appears to exert its anti-inflammatory effects by reducing the production of inflammatory mediators called prostaglandins. It is metabolized by the liver to inactive metabolites. Naproxen acts as a non-selective cyclooxygenase (COX) inhibitor by reversibly inhibiting the COX-1 and COX-2 enzymes^{6,7}. This inhibits prostaglandin synthesis. Prostaglandins act as signaling molecules in the body and induce

inflammation. Thus, naproxen induces anti-inflammatory effects by inhibiting COX-1/2. The purpose of this study was to formulate development and in vitro evaluation of a bilayer tablet dosage form containing a fixed-dose combination of naratriptan and naproxen as an immediate-release layer and a sustained-release layer containing naratriptan to achieve both Optimal plasma levels of the drug persist and over longer periods of time.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials: Naproxen and Naratriptan were obtained as gift samples from Alembic pharmaceuticals Ltd., Gujarat. Sodium starch glycolate, Croscarmellose, Lactose, Starch, Magnesium Stearate, Talc, Tamarind seed polysaccharide, Hydroxypropyl methylcellulose K100, Hydroxypropyl methylcellulose K15, Microcrystalline cellulose, Polyvinylpyrrolidone, Magnesium stearate all other chemicals used were of analytical grade.

Methods

Characterizations of immediate release (IR) and sustain release (SR) granules:

Both IR and SR particles were evaluated for various parameters prior to compression. Since naproxen tablets are manufactured by dry granulation techniques, only the LOD of naratriptan granules was measured. The angle of repose was measured by the fixed funnel method. Bulk and tap densities were determined using a tap densitometer, compressibility index and Hausner ratio were calculated according to USP guidelines.

Evaluation of drug-excipient compatibility study in stability chamber:

Compatibility studies of naratriptan and naproxen with possible excipients were conducted using single and binary mixtures of API and excipients, both formulated mixtures were prepared and packaged in glass vials and formulated. With rubber stopper and low density polyethylene (LDPE) locking. The samples were stored at room temperature ($25^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $60\% \pm 5\%$ relative humidity), accelerated conditions ($40^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $75\% \pm 5\%$ relative humidity), and 50°C for one month. Puncture LDPE plugs under accelerated conditions ($40^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $75\% \pm 5\%$ relative humidity).

Drug-excipient compatibility studies by FTIR:

The compatibility of drugs with their respective excipients was studied by FTIR spectroscopy. The scanning was performed 20 times for both Naratriptan and Naproxen with resolution of 1 cm^{-1} over the region of $4000\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The scans were evaluated for the presence of principle

peaks of drug, shifting and masking of drug peaks and appearance of new peaks due to polymer interaction.

Formulation development of immediate release Naratriptan tablets:

Table 1: Formulation design of Naratriptan immediate release tablets

S. No	Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8
1	Naratriptan	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
2	Sodium starch glycolate	1.5	2.25	3.0	3.75	-	-	-	-
3	Croscarmellose	-	-	-	-	1.5	2.25	3.0	3.75
4	Lactose	96	95.25	94.5	94.75	96	95.25	94.5	94.75
5	Starch (5 %)	qs	qs	qs	qs	qs	qs	qs	qs
6	Magnesium Stearate	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.75
7	Talc	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.75
8	Total weight (mg)	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

Table 2: Formulation for the optimized preparation of Naproxen (250 mg) extended release tablets

S. No	INGREDIENTS (mg)	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8	C9	C10	C11	C12	C13	C14	C15
1	Naproxen	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250
2	Tamarind seed polysaccharide	10	20	30	40	50	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
3	Hydroxypropyl methylcellulose K100	-	-	-	-	-	10	20	30	40	50	-	-	-	-	-
4	Hydroxypropyl methylcellulose K15	--	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	10	20	30	40	50
5	Microcrystallinecellulose	225	215	205	195	185	225	215	205	195	185	225	215	205	195	185
6	Polyvinylpyrrolidone	qs														
7	Magnesium stearate	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
8	Talc	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
9	Total	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500

Evaluation of pre formulation parameters⁸,

All the formulations were evaluated for flow properties independently at both pre-granulation and pre-compression stages. The fixed funnel method was employed to measure the angle of repose. Bulk and tapped densities were determined by tapped density apparatus from which compressibility index and Hausner's ratio values were calculated

Evaluation of Multi-layered tablets**Weight Variation⁹**

Ten tablets were selected at random and weighed individually. Average weight was calculated and standard deviation was computed.

Hardness¹⁰

Hardness is termed as the tablet crushing strength and it is the force required to break a tablet diametrically. Hardness of tablets was measured by selecting 5 tablets randomly and the hardness of each tablet was measured with Pfizer hardness tester. It is usually measured in terms of kg/cm².

Friability¹¹

Ten tablets were weighed and placed in the friabilator, which was then operated for 25 revolutions per minute. After 4 minutes, the tablets were dusted and reweighed. The percentage friability was determined using the formula,

Percentage friability = $\frac{\text{Initial weight} - \text{Final weight}}{\text{Initial weight}} \times 100$

Disintegration Time^{12,13}

The disintegration time of the tablets was determined as per Indian pharmacopoeia. The test was carried out using tablet disintegration apparatus. Distilled water was used as a disintegrating media at 35-39 °C. The time required to obtain complete disintegration of all the tablets was noted.

Drug Content¹⁴

Ten tablets were crushed in a mortar and following procedure carried out.

Drug Content for Naratriptan

Preparations equivalent to 10 mg was weighed accurately and transferred to 100ml volumetric flask and dissolved in 0.1N HCl. The volume was made up to the mark with 0.1N HCl. Absorbance of the resulting solution was measured at 281 nm using appropriate blank solution. The drug content was estimated using calibration curve.

Drug Content for Naproxen

Preparations equivalent to 20mg was weighed accurately and transferred to 100ml volumetric flask and dissolved in 7.4 phosphate buffer. The volume was made up to the mark with 7.4 phosphate buffer. Absorbance of the resulting solution was measured at 332 nm using appropriate blank solution. The drug content was estimated using calibration curve.

In-vitro Dissolution Studies

Dissolution test device DS 800 was used to conduct in vitro dissolution investigations (Lab India, Mumbai). Table 5 shows the dissolution criteria for all types of tablets examined. For the first 30 minutes of tablet dissolving, 0.1N HCl was employed as the dissolution media, followed by 7.4 PH phosphate buffers for the remaining duration. At predefined intervals, 5mL samples were extracted and replaced with 5mL of fresh dissolving medium. Whenever necessary, the collected samples were diluted with dissolving fluid before being tested for Naratriptan at 281nm and Naproxen at 332nm using a Double beam UV Visible Spectrophotometer SL 164. (Elico, Hyderabad).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1: FTIR spectrum of Naratriptan pure drug

Figure 2: FTIR spectrum of Naratriptan with excipients

Figure 3: FTIR spectrum Naproxen pure drug

Figure 4: FTIR spectrum of Naproxen with excipients

Drug-drug and drug-excipient compatibility studies

Compatibility studies by physical observation in stability chamber:

After one month, the stability chamber samples of drug-drug and drug-excipient were collected. Any physical changes in look or odour were explored. At room temperature (25 °C $\pm$ 2 °C & 60% RH), all individuals and combinations met the specifications, but at accelerated open temperature (40 °C $\pm$ 2 °C & 75% RH), most of the combinations showed sensitivity (e.g. discoloration, bad odour, and lump formation), while only Naratriptan: Croscarmellose and Naproxen: Tamarind seed polysaccharide (1:1) at 50°C showed lump formation and bad odour.

Compatibility studies by FTIR:

The peaks of tamarind seed polysaccharide absorption were identified at 1036 cm^{-1} (C-O-C, ether group absorbance), 1637 and 1655 cm^{-1} (C=O, aldehyde absorption), 2924 cm^{-1} (C-H stretching), 3356 cm^{-1} (primary OH), and 3385 cm^{-1} (secondary OH), indicating that the separated product was polysaccharide. There has been no change in the shift of the drug's principal peaks (C=O str, C-H str, OH- str).. **Figure 1-4.**

Table 3: Evaluation of pre compression parameters of immediate release tablets Naratriptan

S. No	Parameters	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8
1	Bulk density (g/ml)	0.40 $\pm$ 0.01	0.44 $\pm$ 0.02	0.48 $\pm$ 0.03	0.49 $\pm$ 0.03	0.47 $\pm$ 0.02	0.46 $\pm$ 0.01	0.42 $\pm$ 0.02	0.44 $\pm$ 0.02
2	Tapped density (g/ml)	0.44 $\pm$ 0.02	0.54 $\pm$ 0.01	0.50 $\pm$ 0.01	0.49 $\pm$ 0.01	0.47 $\pm$ 0.01	0.47 $\pm$ 0.02	0.43 $\pm$ 0.02	0.46 $\pm$ 0.02
3	Carr's index (%)	10.3 $\pm$ 1.22	11.7 $\pm$ 1.32	11.5 $\pm$ 2.32	10.43 $\pm$ 1.34	11.04 $\pm$ 1.66	11.76 $\pm$ 1.67	11.54 $\pm$ 1.76	11.36 $\pm$ 1.23
4	Hausner's ratio	1.11 $\pm$ 0.02	1.13 $\pm$ 0.07	1.15 $\pm$ 0.08	1.14 $\pm$ 0.07	1.13 $\pm$ 0.05	1.12 $\pm$ 0.05	1.12 $\pm$ 0.04	1.24 $\pm$ 0.05
5	Angle of repose	29.67 $\pm$ 3.45	27.74 $\pm$ 3.54	28.57 $\pm$ 3.78	29.63 $\pm$ 3.78	29.75 $\pm$ 2.79	28.9 $\pm$ 2.56	29.05 $\pm$ 2.94	29.55 $\pm$ 2.56

Table 4: Evaluation of pre compression parameters of sustained release tablets Naproxen

S	Param	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8	C9	C10	C11	C12	C13	C14	C15
1	Bulk density (g/ml)	0.53±0.03	0.53±0.08	0.59±0.07	0.58±0.04	0.52±0.05	0.51±0.04	0.56±0.06	0.53±0.05	0.53±0.06	0.50±0.04	0.57±0.04	0.58±0.05	0.53±0.07	0.57±0.07	0.58±0.07
2	Tappe d density (g/ml)	0.596±0.06	0.596±0.09	0.592±0.07	0.598±0.04	0.578±0.03	0.500±0.02	0.592±0.06	0.596±0.02	0.596±0.04	0.500±0.04	0.578±0.06	0.598±0.06	0.596±0.03	0.578±0.07	0.598±0.07
3	Carr's index(%)	10.45±1.23	10.45±1.54	10.23±1.67	10.34±1.98	10.25±1.56	10.19±1.76	10.23±1.98	10.45±1.43	10.45±1.34	10.19±1.87	10.25±1.97	10.34±1.56	10.45±1.34	10.25±1.23	10.34±1.67
4	Hausner's ratio	1.13±0.02	1.13±0.03	1.15±0.07	1.18±0.09	1.17±0.05	1.16±0.04	1.15±0.03	1.13±0.04	1.13±0.06	1.16±0.04	1.17±0.07	1.18±0.05	1.13±0.04	1.17±0.06	1.18±0.03
5	Angle of repose (°)*	29.62±2.34	29.62±2.56	29.43±2.56	29.12±2.87	28.96±2.76	28.16±2.78	29.43±2.75	29.62±2.54	29.62±2.74	28.16±2.45	28.96±2.34	29.12±2.67	29.62±2.98	28.96±2.75	29.12±2.55

Pre-compression parameters

The Pre-compression parameters Naratriptan and Naproxen were evaluated for their bulk density, tapped density, compressibility index and Hausner's ratio, and angle of repose, as shown in **Table 3 and 4**. The bulk densities were found to be in the range of 0.4 to 0.58gm/ml. The angle of repose varied from 26 to 29. The low values of angle of repose indicate the free flowing nature of the poeder. The tapped densities ranged 0.45 to 0.99 gm/ml and the Carr's indexes were in the range of 10 to 11. Hausner's ratio was found in the range of 1.12 to 1.18 was found.

Table 5: Evaluation of post compression parameters of immediate release tablets Naratriptan

Sr. No	Parameters	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8
1	Weight variation (mg)	100±	100±	101±	100±	100±	100±	100±	100±
		0.25	0.26	0.35	0.25	0.35	0.12	0.25	0.22
3	Friability (%)	0.60±0.0	0.48±0.0	0.64±	0.57±	0.62±0.	0.51±0.	0.64±0.	0.57±0.
		2	4	0.06	0.07	05	05	07	06
4	Hardness (Kg/cm)	3.8±	3.6±	3.4±	3.5±	3.6±	3.4±	3.4±	3.5±
		0.21	0.22	0.43	0.32	0.44	0.33	0.24	0.32
7	Content uniformity (%)	96.3±	93.5	93.2	97.4±	94.3±	99.1±	97.4±	94.3±
		1.85	±1.64	±1.63	2.12	2.41	1.13	2.12	2.41

Table 6: Evaluation of post compression parameters of sustained release tablets Naproxen

S. n	Parameters	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8	C9	C10	C11	C12	C13	C14	C14
1	Hardness(kg/cm²)	5.5±0.23	6.7±0.12	7.4±0.87	6.2±0.23	6.1±0.65	5.4±0.56	6.7±0.12	6.1±0.65	7.4±0.87	6.2±0.23	6.1±0.65	7.4±0.87	7.4±0.87	5.5±0.23	6.7±0.12
3	Friability (%)	0.15±0.01	0.26±0.05	0.28±0.04	0.30±0.03	0.34±0.02	0.17±0.01	0.26±0.05	0.34±0.02	0.28±0.04	0.30±0.03	0.34±0.02	0.28±0.04	0.28±0.04	0.15±0.01	0.26±0.05
4	Weight variation (%)	0.29±0.02	0.14±0.01	0.13±0.02	0.22±0.01	0.34±0.03	0.35±0.01	0.23±0.02	0.25±0.01	0.26±0.01	0.23±0.03	0.22±0.02	0.21±0.02	0.23±0.01	0.25±0.03	0.21±0.01
5	Content uniformity (%)	97.5±1.23	96.8±2.78	96.5±3.56	98.3±1.32	95.7±3.24	97.4±3.34	96.8±2.78	95.7±3.24	96.5±3.56	98.3±1.32	95.7±3.24	96.5±3.56	96.5±3.56	97.5±1.23	96.8±2.78

Post-compression parameters

Wet granulation was used to make bilayer pills of Naratriptan and Naproxen.

The weight variation, hardness, friability, and drug content uniformity of the produced tablets were assessed, and the results are provided in Tables 5 and 6. The readings that were found to be within the prescribed limits ranged from 0.09 to 0.024%. The hardness ranged from 3.10 to 7.4 kg/cm². Friability was determined to be less than 1% in all batches, indicating the produced tablets' ability to endure shock during transportation and handling. The drug content in the manufactured batches was consistent, ranging from 93.21 to 96.84 percent. ***In vitro***

Dissolution study:

Figure 5: *In vitro* Dissolution of formulation No. F1 – F8 (Naratriptan)

Figure 6: *In vitro* Dissolution of formulation No. C1 – C7 (Naproxen)

Figure 7: *In vitro* Dissolution of formulation No. C8 – C15 (Naproxen)

In vitro dissolution studies were conducted using Dissolution test apparatus DS 800 (Lab India, Mumbai). The dissolution specifications for all types of tablets tested were given in the table 5. For dissolution of Multi-layered tablets, 0.1N HCl was used as dissolution medium for the first 30min and 7.4 P^H phosphate buffers for the remaining time. From the results, drug release of Naratriptan immediate release layer was found to be 98.64±2.34% in 30 minutes and that of the Naproxen sustain release layer was 98.47±0.05% at the end of 12 hours and values are represented in the **Figure 5, 6 & 7**.

Table 7: Release profiles of Naratriptan (F4) and Naproxen (C12) from bilayer tablets in various models.

Drug	Zero order	First order	Higuchi	Korsmeyer-Peppas	Hixson-Crowel
	R ²	R ²	R ²	R ²	R ²
F4	0.909	0.947	0.896	0.995	0.471
C12	0.995	0.770	0.95	0.995	0.859

Release kinetics

The data suggested that the release kinetics of the drugs Naratriptan and Naproxen follows first order drug release, as the values of regression coefficient obtained were highest for Korsmeyer-Peppas drug release profiles (R²=0.995 and 0.995). Results were showed in **Table 7**.

CONCLUSION

The current work revealed the creation and evaluation of an anti-migraine and NSAIDS bilayer tablet in a single dosage form. The immediate release layer of Naratriptan was prepared by direct compression using various super disintegrants, with the optimized formula (F4) containing Croscarmellose sodium as a super disintegrant, and the sustained release layer of Naproxen was prepared by wet granulation using various release retarding agents, with the optimised formula (C12) containing a combination of Tamarind seed polysaccharide release retardants. The Naratriptan and Naproxen bilayered tablets made with sodium starch glycolate and Croscarmellose sodium demonstrated immediate release of the Naratriptan layer after 25 minutes (F4 and F8). The second layer, which was made with Tamarind seed polysaccharide (F 12), had a 12-hour sustained release. Formulations (F16, F22, F28) using HPMC Grades (K100M, K15M, K4M). From the stability studies Bilayer tablets with tamarind seed polysaccharide were found to be stable.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest

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